

Variations in Soil Engineering Properties and Mitigating Roadside Erosion along Naze–Obinze Road in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

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Received: August 16, 2024; Accepted: November 6, 2024; Published: December 4, 2024.

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14277925>

Abstract: In this study, variations in the engineering properties of soil at erosion sites along Naze–Obinze Road in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria, were determined to propose measures for mitigating roadside erosion. Roadside erosion along the road network was identified, classified, and mapped out in intervals of 1 km to determine the magnitude of the problem in specific areas. The traffic pavement and the road shoulder were damaged to various degrees, and the side and back slopes were altered owing to surface material loss, gullying, and increased quantities of sediments, leading to ditch clogging with the consequent development of potholes and flooding. The most severe roadside erosion occurred at KM 10 (the riverine area) and in areas with heavy vehicle movements. The least severe erosion occurred at KM 8. The shear strengths of the soil at the highest- and least-eroded points were 122.8 and 134.5 kN/m², respectively. Overall, erosion occurred more in the areas without drainage (KM 1, 3, 6, and 7) than in the areas with scanty drainage (KM 4 and 11). Proposed erosion control measures include maintenance of drainage channels, construction of new drainage channels, ditches, and retention ponds, provision of check dams, and grassing road verges.

Keywords: Roadside erosion; Cohesion; Shear strength; Erodibility; Erosion control

Introduction

Soil erosion is the process by which rock particles or soil particles are detached from a site, transported, and deposited at another location. The eroded particles may be transported by water, wind, or ice. Human activities and interference, such as

deforestation, bush burning, construction, and urbanisation, are drivers of erosion (Borrelli et al., 2020; Maronedze & Schütt, 2020). Belle (1971) developed a simple classification method for identifying and mapping erosion and quantifying the extent of the problem. Gully erosion by water is caused by the

removal of vegetation cover and deforestation, diversion of runoff into a cover or channel, abrupt termination of concrete channels, defective design and construction of channels, delinquent blockage of concrete drains and channels, arbitrary housing development, road narrow pit, poor erosion control, quarry building sand/stones, and inappropriate farming practices (Barbara, 1995). Gullies are small channels formed on a land surface by rainwater, particularly a narrow valley, resulting from heavy rain downpours (Chandrakala et al., 2020). Raindrops strike on the bare soil, which can detach and split the soil into fine particles. These particles are transported in suspensions by running water as sheet erosion down the slope. Gullies are formed when rills combine and develop such that they cannot be eliminated via typical tillage operations (Torri & Borselli, 2000). Gullies can be classified according to cross-sectional morphology, such as triangular, rectangular, trapezoidal, U-shaped, V-shaped, and wedge-shaped shapes (Thwaites et al., 2022). Gully erosion is a severe geo-environmental problem that causes land degradation and threatens the safety of humans, wildlife, and infrastructure.

During roadside erosion, the surface material along the edge of a road is removed by water, wind, or ice. The rate of roadside erosion

depends on several factors. According to Barbara (1995), the factors are climatic (for example, the amount and intensity of precipitation, average temperature, temperature variation, wind speed, and storm frequency), geologic factors (for example, the sediment or rock type, rock porosity and permeability, and land slope), and biological (for example, ground cover from vegetation and the types of organisms inhabiting the area). Roadside erosion occurs on road slopes in tropical regions exposed to high-intensity rainfall, causing slope failures (Knights et al., 2020). Roadside erosions can reduce road widths and destroy roadside structures by damaging the entrance to residential and commercial buildings. These lead to the clogging of ditches, with the consequent development and expansion of potholes on road surfaces. Hence, erosion control in tropical regions is critical, given the high runoff coupled with changes in the local soil characteristics.

A survey of the roadside erosion between Naze and Ihiagwa was first conducted in the early 1970s (Udoha, 2012). The field survey at the time was limited to mapping and providing quantitative measures of the extent of erosion and deposition in the paved road network. The rate at which roadside erosion occurs along Naze–Obinze area is high,

particularly during the rainy season. Erosion control policies have not been a traditionally formulated part of highway programmes in Imo State, which is exposed to high and frequent rainfall. Roadside seeding by the residents in the area and evidence of the erosion-control design of structures and embankments are lacking. Most portions of the slopes were inadequately compacted and completed, forming deep holes and exposing the involved areas to severe danger. The roadside erosion along Naze–Obinze road has damaged nearby residential and commercial buildings, depositing sediments around the area. Some construction sites were left unprotected and, consequently, remained vulnerable to erosion, causing the wearing away of the topsoil until a vegetation cover was established naturally. Some of these eroded materials flow into and pollute the nearby Otammiri River. This problem has not been investigated adequately, and no policy has been implemented by relevant authorities to prevent roadside erosion.

The aim of this study is to investigate measures for controlling roadside erosion along Naze–Obinze Road. Field investigations and laboratory tests were conducted to analyse the roadside erosion along Naze–Obinze Road by mapping and providing quantitative measures of the extent

of the roadside erosion and deposition along the paved road network from Naze to Obinze. In addition, the extent of the shoulder, side-slope, and back-slope erosions were computed, and the most eroded area was determined. The causes and effects of roadside erosion along the Naze–Obinze Road were analysed. Control measures for the roadside erosion along the Naze–Obinze Road are recommended for implementation by the government and other relevant stakeholders to improve transportation and safety for commuters and residents.

Materials and Methods

Study area

The Naze–Obinze road is in Owerri-West Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria. It is a state road, also classified as a “Trunk Road B,” with a single-lane carriageway at the time of the study. This road is a part of the Owerri Ring Road, which links the Owerri–Aba and Owerri–Port Harcourt highways, covering a distance of approximately 13 km. Fig. 1 shows the Google map of the road, which starts from the Naze junction of the Owerri Ring Road and ends at the Federal University of Technology, Owerri (FUTO) junction in Obinze. The study area has flat and undulating topography with less dense vegetation owing to numerous previous and

ongoing land development projects. The area is highly populated because of higher educational institutions (the Federal Polytechnic, Nekede [FPN] and FUTO) located in the area; thus, the area has a higher rate of vehicular movement than surrounding

communities. The location of the roadside erosion of Naze–Obinze Road is close to the residence of rural dwellers in Nekede, Ihiagwa, and Obinze.

Fig. 1 Map of the study area (Source: <https://www.google.com/maps>)

Site investigation

First, the roadside erosion sites along Naze–Obinze road were visited for relevant measurements. This was achieved via physical observations, and references were made to existing records related to the project area or immediate environments sharing common geographical conditions.

Next, sites were selected across the entire length of the road (a total of approximately 13

km) in intervals of 1 km, starting from Naze junction up to Obinze junction. The distances were measured using a 30-m-long measurement tape and pegs with the support of a follower. The eroded areas were identified and captured using a camera, indicating the class of roadside erosion at the locations (that is, whether it occurred at the shoulder, side slope, or back slope and whether it occurred on one or both sides of

the road). Field measurements were performed to determine the shoulder width, lengths of the side and back slopes, gully size, and depth and surface extent of the deposit across the ditch. Photographs of some of the

measurements at the erosion sites are shown in Fig. 2. A schematic of the road cross-section is shown in Fig. 3. The roadside erosion was classified according to Belle (1971), as listed in Table 1.

Fig. 2 Measurements conducted at some erosion sites: (a) Measurement of back slope of advanced gully erosion at KM 10; (b) Measurement of width of eroded shoulder at KM 8.

Fig. 3 Schematic of Naze–Obinze Road cross-section

Table 1 Classification of roadside erosion

Class of erosion	Description
Erosion class 1 (E ₁)	Sheet erosion. Minute rivulets are occasionally present.
Erosion class 2 (E ₂)	Rill erosion. Rill patterns appear, with rills up to 0.15 m deep.
Erosion class 3 (E ₃)	Initial gully erosion. Presence of numerous small gullies between 0.15 and 0.3 m deep.
Erosion class 4 (E ₄)	Marked gully erosion. Presence of numerous gullies between 0.3 and 0.6 m deep.
Erosion class 5 (E ₅)	Advanced erosion. Presence of gullies or depressions exceeding depths of 0.6 m.

Collection and testing of soil samples

Soil samples were collected along Naze–Obinze road using an auger on Thursday, 14 April 2011, between 10.00 am and 11.00 am. The samples were collected from the highest-eroded section (KM 10), close to the Otammiri River, which was the least-eroded section (KM 8), and the point where no erosion occurred (the reference section). The auger was drilled in the highest- and least-eroded points up to a depth of 0.6 m. The collected samples were transferred to a measuring pan using a palette knife and transported to the erosion laboratory at FUTO for testing.

Tests were performed on the samples to determine the angle of internal friction (Φ) and soil cohesion (C). The experimental system consisted of a shear box, stopwatch, weighing balance, measuring pan, glass plate,

60 mm × 60 mm × 20 mm sample ring, shear box cell, and weights. For each undisturbed soil sample, the soil was filled in the 60 mm × 60 mm × 20 mm sample ring and carefully placed in the shear box cell. The soil sample was trimmed to suit the internal dimensions of the shear box, and the moisture content of the sample was determined from the resultant cuttings. Next, the metal plates were inserted into the shear box adjacent to the upper and lower faces of the sample. The weight of the hanger applying vertical normal stress to the sample was assembled with the dial gauge to record the horizontal displacements. Locating screws, which aligned the two split halves of the box, were removed. An appropriate gear was selected for the required application rate of the horizontal shear forces. The shearing of the sample was started and recorded in intervals of 30 s. Moving-ring dial gauge (horizontal) readings were obtained

throughout the test until shear failure, signified by the splitting of the sample into two halves in the shear box (Fig. 4). The entire procedure was repeated for two similar specimens of the same sample, each with an increased normal load applied during the horizontal shearing of the sample.

Based on the generated data, the normal and shear stresses were computed from the shear stress–normal stress graph. The soil cohesion, c , was interpreted as the intercept on the vertical (shear stress) axis for the highest-

eroded point, least-eroded point, and reference point. The angle of internal friction, Φ , was deduced as the slope of the curve. For soils, the shear strength equation is expressed as follows (Garg, 2013):

$$\tau_f = c + \sigma_n \tan \varphi \quad (1)$$

where τ is the shear strength, c is the cohesion, σ_n is the maximum normal stress, and φ is the angle of internal friction. Equation (1) is known as Coulomb's equation and is used to determine the total shear strength of a given soil mass.

Fig. 4 Recording of time and dial gauge readings

Results and Discussion

Comparison of soil properties in eroded areas

The cohesion, angle of internal friction, shear strength, and maximum shear strength of the soil at different sections of the road were

determined. Table 2 lists the properties of soil along critical sections of the road. The highest-eroded, least-eroded, and reference areas were located at KM 10, KM 8, and KM 1, respectively.

Table 2 Soil properties at critical sections

Area	c (kN/m ²)	Φ (°)	τ (kN/m ²)	τ_{\max} (kN/m ²)
Highest-eroded area	6	37	122.8	141.8
Least-eroded area	10	35	134.5	155.0
Reference area	4	40	153.2	160.8

The erodibility at the highest-eroded point was higher than at the least-eroded point (Table 2). Therefore, the maximum shear stress at the least-eroded point was higher than that at the highest-eroded point. The higher the shear stress from the highest-eroded point, the lower the eroded area. Regarding the cohesion results, the cohesion from the least-eroded point was higher than that at the highest point, whereas the angle of internal friction from the highest-eroded point was higher than that at the least-eroded point (Table 2). Erodibility at the least-eroded point was lower than that at the highest-eroded point. As the rainfall duration increases, erodibility increases from the highest-eroded point. Therefore, the higher the soil cohesion, the lower the angle of internal friction.

Because the least- and highest-eroded points have positive soil cohesion and angle of internal friction values, both soils are cohesive frictional soils because both the soil cohesion and the angle of internal friction range between 1 and ∞ (Arora, 2010). Although these soils are cohesive frictional

soils, erosion occurred in most areas owing to physical factors. These factors include high runoff concentration, steep slopes of the area, inadequate drainage channels, blockage of concrete drains, and arbitrary housing development.

The angle of internal friction of the reference area was higher than those of the highest and lowest eroded areas. This indicates that the soil in the reference area is less porous (or more compact) than the highest and lowest eroded areas. In contrast, the cohesion of the reference area was lower than those of the highest and lowest eroded areas. Furthermore, the maximum shear strength of the reference area exceeded those of the lowest and highest points.

Extent of roadside erosion

The extent of the roadside erosion along Naze–Obinze road in Owerri-West Local Government Area, Imo State, is described in this section. The surface area values of the extent of damage on the shoulder, side slopes, and back slopes along the Naze–Obinze Road

are listed in Table 3. The specific remarks for each interval length of 1 km are presented in Table 4.

E₁ occurred at the shoulder in KM 1, and the area of the eroded shoulder was high (2325 m²). Moreover, at the side slope, E₂ was relatively low (45 m²). At KM 4, E₁ was very high at the shoulder, E₂ was relatively high, but E₃, E₄, and E₅ did not occur. Only E₂ occurred at the side slope, whereas E₃ occurred at the back slope. Hence, erosion

occurred more in the areas without drainage (KM 1, KM 3, KM 6, and KM 7) than in the areas with scanty drainage (KM 4 and KM 11). Erosion occurred at two points where scanty drainage channels were located, whereas it occurred at four different points without drainage channels from the distance along the stretch of the area of study. Photographs of some erosion sites along the Naze–Obinze Road are shown in Fig. 5(a) - (d).

Table 3 Extent of roadside erosion at shoulders, side slopes, and back slopes

Erosion class	Eroded area (m ²)												
	1 ^a	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
<i>Shoulder erosion</i>													
E ₁ **	2325	1650	2625	1575	1890	1875	2130	1270	2390	2410	2650	1570	2275
E ₂	-	22.4	-	380	470	20.5	570	-	-	49	12	28.8	-
E ₃	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
E ₄	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
E ₅	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	2325	1672.4	2625	1955	2360	1895.5	2700	1270	2390	2459	2662	1598.8	2275
<i>Side-slope erosion</i>													
E ₁	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	216	11.7	-	-	-	-
E ₂	45	26.9	21.5	64.5	80	240	127.2	-	-	160	38.5	15.5	53
E ₃	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	320	-	-	-
E ₄	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	-	-
E ₅	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	45	26.9	21.5	64.5	80	240	127.2	216	11.7	480	46.5	15.5	53
<i>Back-slope erosion</i>													
E ₁	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
E ₂	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
E ₃	-	-	-	42.5	-	-	-	-	-	450	-	-	-
E ₄	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	14.6	-	-
E ₅	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	165	-	-	-
Total	-	-	-	42.5	-	-	-	-	-	615	14.6	-	-
Total hectares	0.24	0.17	0.26	0.21	0.24	0.21	0.28	0.15	0.24	0.36	0.27	0.16	0.23
* The numbers represent the kilometre intervals. For example, 1 indicates KM 1, 2 indicates KM 2, 3 indicates KM 3, etc.													
** E ₁ –E ₅ represent the classes of erosion listed in Table 1													

Table 4 Specific remarks for each eroded area

Erosion area	Remarks
KM 1	KM 1 started from Naze junction linking Aba–Owerri Road. Both sheet and rill erosion were observed. The area had commercial buildings and a garage with plain topography. The eroded portion was significantly large.
KM 2	Sheet and rill erosion were observed in KM 2. The area was mainly a vegetation area. The area may be further eroded in the future owing to activities induced by the Small-Scale Industrial Clusters sited there by the Imo State Government.
KM 3	In KM 3, the shoulder was slightly affected because of the low level of the highway. Accumulated water (ponds) existed owing to a lack of drainage
KM 4	KM 4 is a busy section of the highway where the FPN junction, River-Side bus stop, and Great Mission Church are sited. The roads leading to these entrances were eroded. Some portions of the area were highly vegetated, with sloppy topography. Initial gully erosion occurred at the Rose Bar. Scanty drainage was found in the area.
KM 5	Both sheet and rill erosion occurred here. KM 5 was a residential area with an untarred road leading to Umuoma Community; hence the road entrance was significantly eroded.
KM 6	KM 6 comprised the Nekede Police Post as well as residential and commercial areas, making the entrance of this road to be highly eroded. Moreover, no drainage channel was constructed in this area.
KM 7	More eroded areas were observed in KM 7 compared to previous areas due to the Ihiagwa Market and bus stop, which led to frequent vehicular movement while conveying FUTO students. Inappropriate water channelling around the area resulted in irregular water accumulation due to a lack of drainage.
KM 8	Only sheet erosion occurred at KM 8. KM 8 was a residential and commercial area, with a road leading to the FUTO back gate. Water accumulated in front of the Ice Box bar.
KM 9	KM 9 was a residential area with plain topography. No rapid movement of runoff occurred in the area, and only sheet erosion was observed.
KM 10	KM 10 was a riverine area (Otammiri River) and a forest area. The area has a sloppy terrain with a high runoff velocity, which resulted in soil-particle detachment and transportation. Despite worn-out drainage channels, sheet, rill, initial gully, and advanced gully erosion were observed.
KM 11	KM 11 was a riverine area. Some portions were hilly, with high runoff velocity, which affected the road. However, KM 11 was an undeveloped area with worn-out drainage channels. Sheet, rill, and marked gully erosion occurred here.
KM 12	KM 12 was mostly an undeveloped, vegetation area, with a road leading to FUTO front gate. The area was not significantly affected by the roadside erosion.
KM 13	KM 13 marked the end of the Naze–Obinze Road at the Obinze junction. It was a commercial and vegetation area. The area had no slope and was minimally affected by roadside erosion.

Fig. 5 (a) Eroded width of road shoulder at KM 4; (b) Sloping entrance to a building at KM 4; (c) Sloping area at KM 10, near Otammiri River; (d) Damaged drainage channel at KM 10

The variation in the eroded area with the distance along the stretch of the road was analysed (Fig. 6). The roadside erosion was most severe at KM 10, which was a riverine area. This could be attributed to the sloping terrain in the area, which increased the run-off velocity and caused the detachment and transportation of soil particles, creating gullies around the area.

Fig. 6 Variation in eroded area with distance along stretch of road

Causes of Roadside Erosion Along Naze–Obinze Road

Remote causes

Steep slope and length: The slope of the area stretching from KM 10 downstream was high. Generally, steep slopes facilitate a high flow velocity and, consequently, increase the roadside erosion capacity of runoff.

Land use and development: Human activities, particularly activities geared toward land development, remotely caused roadside erosion. Many buildings have been erected in the area recently. These buildings are clustered upstream and along the affected road area. These buildings, with corrugated roofs, generate large volumes of runoff, which eventually find their way onto the roads of lower elevation.

Immediate causes

Runoff concentration: Phenomenal convergence of all runoffs from various parts of the area upstream, including private premises, occurred at the roadsides owing to the existing topography in the area. This led to the concentration of overland flow. This flow type weakens and easily loosens the soils along its flow path. With its high erosive velocity, the materials were eventually washed away and deposited, possibly at relatively lower downstream levels.

Absence of lined drainage system: No lined drainage system was constructed to safely conduct overland flow. The earth drains, likely constructed by the inhabitants and the local government council, have remained unlined and a source of rill and gully erosion development, particularly on sloping surfaces.

Effects of Roadside Erosion Along Naze–Obinze Road

The roadside erosion in the study area severely affects the roadside, road structure, existing structures near the roadside, road users, and the government. The effects are as follows.

Roadside width reduction: Increased water erosion on the roadside contributed to the road width reduction. The continuous detachment of the roadside materials by water and wind reduced the road width owing to inadequate construction of the shoulders, the use of substandard materials, inappropriate drainage channel, and poor management.

Roadside deterioration: The changes in the shape, size, and width of the road owing to roadside erosion is attributed to inadequate drainage channels. This caused water bars to discharge roadside erosion water and induce water accumulation on the road.

Traffic congestion: The roadside erosion has caused the congestion of vehicles along the Naze–Obinze Road. Because the roadside was damaged and the roadside width decreased, traffic did not flow freely, leading to congestion of vehicles on the road. This also delayed transportation, spoiling goods and exposing passengers to road accident risk.

Damage to nearby structures: Generally, structures were located close to the road, adversely affected by erosion. In some cases, the foundations of the buildings were exposed, making them prone to collapse.

High cost of road maintenance: Roadside erosion leads to frequent reconstruction and rehabilitation of the road. This is uneconomical and should be prevented.

Measures for Roadside Erosion Control Along Naze–Obinze Road

Maintenance of existing drainage channels: The roadside erosion in the study area can be controlled if the existing drainage channels are maintained satisfactorily. However, maintenance involves constructing drainage channels, removing water-deposited particles on the channels, removing waste dumped near the roadside, enacting strict regulations guiding waste-disposal management, and providing waste disposal facilities for people

living near the roadside. This will prevent the blocking of drainage channels, which may cause roadside erosion.

Construction of new water drainage channels, ditches, and retention ponds:

Well-designed roadside drains and ditches help control roadside erosion (Yu et al., 2024). The concrete drains must be constructed on both sides of the road to safely transport the runoff. Trapezoidal drainage channels that can handle the discharge of up to 3.1 m³/s should be designed. Moreover, 3,500 m of drains should be provided for the drainage system to have a safe outlet. Culverts should be constructed at determined positions in the area of operations. Hence, a total of 36-m-long culverts should be provided.

Construction of paved ditches in areas without channels or ditches can solve the roadside erosion problem (Alvis et al., 2024; Yu et al., 2024). The ditches should be paved with an inexpensive permeable material, such as coarse gravel or grass, instead of concrete, which might present cost and expansion problems.

Apart from emptying the drains safely into the Otammiri River, it is necessary to use a retention pond as an alternative (Swai, 2022). Two retention ponds, each capable of storing up to 210 m³ of water, should be constructed

at determined safe locations downstream of the basin. The ponds should be sited so that overflows would not harm the inhabitants or damage the environment.

Appropriate siting of bridge: The roadside erosion can be controlled by constructing a bridge at an appropriate location. The bridge should be sited where the water channel is straight and unobstructed. The road can cross the bridge at right angles, with level approaches. The banks should be firm and level. Furthermore, the bridge must be sufficiently high to prevent washout or damage to the underside of the bridge.

Provision of check dams: Check dams are bags typically placed in a roadside ditch and lined with coarse gravel or established vegetation. Check dam provision is an effective soil conservation technique that helps to reduce erosion and flooding (Garg, 2010). The sand should be mixed with cement to improve the durability of the sandbags. Although this approach has minimal costs, it helps reduce water flow and soil erosion in the ditch (Swai, 2022). Some agencies build more durable check dams using earth-moving equipment to place a combination of rock and coarse gravels of period intervals in a roadside ditch. When the roadside ditch runs downhill, check dams should be placed in steps, down from the slope, but not at the

bottom of the hill, where it will be inefficient. The dams should be placed in mostly bare soil rather than in vegetated areas for enhanced effectiveness.

Grassing of road verges: The completed roadside embankment should be protected by grassing its verges. The grassing should be preceded by top soiling for improved results.

Total reclamation of affected area and rehabilitation of Naze–Obinze Road:

Considering the strategic importance of the road and the potential capacity of the area to advance into an urban status, two gully units should be fully reclaimed using suitable filling materials. Filling and compaction need to be performed in layers of 25 cm thickness, ensuring BS 1377 standards. The entire length of the earth road should be fully rehabilitated by filling, levelling, and grading.

Conclusion

The types, factors, causes, and effects of roadside erosion that occurred along the 13-km-long Naze–Obinze road were investigated in this study. Based on the findings, sheet erosion occurred on the road 13 km, rill erosion occurred in some areas, and initial, marked, and advanced erosion occurred in a few areas. At KM 10, severe advanced erosion and marked gully erosion were

observed, which might be attributed to the sloppy terrain that increased run-off movement. This detached the soil surface and transported the granular materials into the Otammiri River. The other portions of the study area were mostly affected by sheet, rill, and initial gully erosion. These resulted in the deterioration of the roadsides and excessive deposition of sediment in the ditches, leading to unsafe motoring conditions. The highest-eroded section was at KM 10 (the riverine area), whereas the least-eroded section was at KM 8. The shear strengths, τ , of the soil were 122.8 and 134.5 kN/m² from the highest- and least-eroded points, respectively. Because the least- and highest-eroded points had positive values of soil cohesion and angle of internal friction, both sections are cohesive frictional soil.

Erosion occurred in most areas due to physical factors, including steep slope and length, land use and development, run-off concentration, and the absence of a lined drainage system. The erosion led to the clogging of ditches, resulting in potholes, flooding, and blocking of concrete drains. Maintenance of existing drainage channels, construction of new water drainage channels, ditches, and retention ponds, appropriate siting of bridges, provision of check dams, and grassing of road verges are proposed for

controlling roadside erosion along Naze–Obinze Road. Early implementation of these measures is recommended to achieve safer conditions for vehicular movements, a more aesthetically pleasing roadside environment, and reduced amounts of roadside sediments from the drainage system. In addition, these measures will minimise the deterioration of the problem and achieve improved cost control.

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